
Collaboration of Local Mass Media and Companies in ExxonMobil Cepu Limited's CSR Communications in Indonesia

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ABSTRACT	ARTICLE DETAILS
<p>CSR communication can be built through two-way exchanges and collaboration with various parties. CSR program information is centralized in the target elite, and there is no communication down to the small units in society, which results in distorted information. The research aims to explore the collaboration model between local mass media and oil and gas companies in communicating CSR to stakeholders. This research used a descriptive qualitative approach with the Yin model case study strategy.</p> <p>Data was collected through interviews with 25 informants consisting of representatives of companies, government, mass media, NGOs implementing programs, and beneficiaries of CSR programs. The research results showed that collaboration between local mass media and companies leads to three patterns: collaborate, involve, and inform. The mechanism for implementing these three patterns, the local mass media in constructing CSR messages focuses on three key sentences: contribution, a form of corporate concern, and a form of good neighbor. The research results also concluded that collaboration between mass media companies and oil and gas companies affected mass media's independence in helping communicate CSR programs to the public.</p> <p>Collaboration fosters self-sufficiency from local mass media networks that voluntarily communicate CSR to the broader public. The relationship between local mass media and companies creates a take-and-give atmosphere where companies and the public try to reach a consensus and collaboration.</p> <p>KEYWORDS: Collaboration, Csr Communication, Local Mass Media, Public Relation.</p>	<p>Published On: 24 January 2026</p> <p>Available on: https://ijiissh.com/</p>

INTRODUCTION

The socially dynamic nature of the oil industry requires companies to be proactive and socially responsible, maintaining their reputation, public legitimacy, and social mechanisms, as well as operating ethically and environmentally friendly. One of the strategies implemented is implementing corporate social responsibility (CSR) as a form of support for sustainable development. CSR is integral to business strategy when organizations operate in new regions and cultures (Anderson & Bieniaszewska, 2005). Thus, CSR is carried out with different targets and issues, adjusted to developments and global trends. This can be seen in studies in China (Liu & Lewis, 2019), Azerbaijan and Kazakhstan (Buldybayeva, 2014) (Gulbrandsen & Moe, 2014), and Nigeria with the issue of defending HIV/AIDS sufferers (Joseph & Elda, 2019), and raising the issue of climate change (Jaworska, 2018). CSR programs are also assumed to be more effective in bridging stakeholder perceptions of the company's social and environmental aspects (Ellerup et al., 2018). By condition, CSR emphasizes the identification, prioritization, and sustainable management of stakeholders. The sustained commitment must be demonstrated locally to facilitate community engagement (Dobele et al., 2014) and crisis-coping strategies that companies present to society, including trust and legitimacy (Ham & Kim, 2019a). From a communication perspective, the implementation of the CSR program will run well and be on target if it is supported by good communication with stakeholders. CSR communication is one of the right ways to ensure that the programs delivered to beneficiaries are right on target in the direction you want to go (Tench et al., 2014). CSR communication can also be understood as communicating the social and environmental impacts of an organization's economic activities on the interest groups and society. Tench et al. (2014) reminded us that in CSR, without communication, information is lost. It is often a problem when companies start CSR programs but fail to communicate with stakeholders and tell the public what they are doing. So, when communicative messages are not delivered, damaged, or lost somewhere in the transmission process, companies waste their CSR efforts. On the other hand, with CSR communication, information exchange will be built. If a CSR program is communicated intentionally or not, it can produce two different effects.

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On the one hand, CSR information can be positive and constructive because the company, as the message's originator and sender, conveys sincere, reliable, and transparent information to stakeholders and the public, which is perceived as it should be. On the other hand, CSR information can be harmful and damage companies because they send false, incorrect, inaccurate, or distorted information, or the message's recipient misunderstands and misconceives the CSR information. Thus, it is essential not only for companies to be involved in the information exchange process but also for the results of CSR communication (Littlejohn et al., 2017).

In the context of public relations, CSR communication also provides the broadest possible access to the public to verify and provide input or criticism for future program development. This is one of the benefits of CSR communication (Kross, 2013), which companies can use to improve their ideal image (Wilcox, 2006); (Tanaya, 2013); (Tanaya, 2004). CSR communication through mass communication also aims to maintain corporate transparency and accountability. However, sometimes, it must be acknowledged that the various CSR images and claims displayed by companies are not always directly proportional to reality (Rahmanto, Andre, 2010).

However, Tench's (2014) theoretical perspective is inversely proportional to oil and gas companies' CSR communication practices in Bojonegoro Regency, East Java Province, Indonesia. In particular, the CSR program from ExxonMobil Cepu Limited (EMCL), in the Banyu Urip oil field in Mojodelik Village, Gayam District, Bojonegoro Regency.

There are two problems with EMCL's CSR communication. The first, CSR program information is centralized in the target village elites. There is a tendency for EMCL to feel that the community has been represented by the village government, especially the village head. Thus, EMCL does not directly communicate with the community but feels that it is sufficient up to the village government. Not all information is conveyed to the community by the village head. Thus, CSR information is distorted.

The second, there is no communication down to the smallest unit. Researchers discovered that companies do not try to inform CSR programs to the smallest units in society. Sometimes, the information conveyed at the village level is not disseminated back to the neighborhood or tahlil congregation. Meanwhile, the targets of CSR programs are mainly in the small units of the village, namely hamlets, community units, and neighborhood units. Locally-based communication channels that can reach more comprehensive levels of society are needed.

Maintaining social relations is essential in implementing CSR programs and must be carried out through participatory communication activities. Good social relations will support increasing public awareness and participation (Widhagdha et al., 2019). This includes opinion leaders in the smallest communities. Opinion leaders can moderate the success of CSR communication through dialogue between companies and local communities (Rizal et al., 2022).

One of the efforts made by companies to ensure effective CSR communication is by synergizing or collaborating with stakeholders. One of them is local mass media. The parties' involvement in CSR communication is essential because communication is vital in successfully implementing CSR programs (Tench et al., 2014).

Apart from increasing the effectiveness of CSR messages, CSR communication through the media can also improve a company's reputation in the eyes of the public, especially if it is interactive. CSR communication through sustainability reports on multinational company websites in India can achieve public reputation (Tewari & Dave, 2012), interactive communication (Yang & Liu, 2020), and commitment to corporate citizenship and sustainable development (Moreno & Capriotti, 2009). The involvement of other sectors in corporate CSR communications can reduce the negative impacts caused by interactions in online media (Ma & Bentley, 2022). Social media can serve as a contemporary and effective means of spreading the message of CSR programs. Social media contributes to developing environmentally conscious communities through strategic CSR collaboration (Pujihartati et al., 2023).

This is where the urgency of research on collaboration between local mass media and companies in EMCL CSR communications becomes essential to fill the existing gaps. This research will explore how the collaboration model between local mass media and companies in CSR communication to stakeholders benefits both parties.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Collaboration in CSR Communication

Companies design and distribute CSR communication about CSR program activities (Morsing, 2006). Company efforts in communicating CSR aim to obtain a positive image, improve reputation, achieve product differentiation, and increase consumer loyalty through CSR programs (Siegel & McWilliams, 2006).

CSR communication is essential because of at least three values (Ihlen et al., 2011). The first, CSR communication brings to mind that the public has different views about CSR and expects different things from organizations. Thus, CSR communication can help explain its implications for corporate communications management. Also, to overcome the complexities and challenges created by public pressure, modernization, rationalization, and social change, communicators need to approach their tasks reflectively with society (Holmström, 2004; van Ruler & Verči, 2005) (Ihlen et al., 2011).

The second, CSR communication studies also provide the possibility of the birth of the idea of dialogue. Dialogue can help understand issues from an economic and ethical perspective and is especially valuable if it can be integrated into overall company

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strategy. Ideally, dialogue also occurs in open negotiation processes where judgments and assumptions are established in an open process (Bohm, 2008) (Ihlen et al., 2011). The third, transparency is part of the moral basis for business behavior. Transparency can help organizations appear as trustworthy actors through CSR communications with the various channels they use (Henriques, 2007). Therefore, CSR communication is essential in leaving a good mark on the company (Ham & Kim, 2019b). CSR communication is assumed to be more effective than others in bridging stakeholders' perceptions of the social and environmental aspects of the companies they operate (Ellerup et al., 2018).

Companies can communicate their CSR initiatives through various channels, including social reports, thematic reports, codes of ethics, websites, stakeholder consultations (dialogue), internal channels, cause marketing, product packaging, mass media and on TV, and points of sale. However, three channels, particularly social reports, websites, and advertising, play a vital role (Rusdianto, 2013, p. 26).

CSR Communication in Grunig's Public Relations Model

CSR communication has a close relationship with public relations. Public relations is part of management activities carried out continuously by an organization or company to maintain and improve a positive image and opinion from the public so that the organization gains trust and support from the public or surrounding community (May Rudy, 2005: 79). The relationship between Public Relations and CSR can be said to contribute to organizations in shaping organizational reputation, maintaining relationships with stakeholders, crisis management, and also ethics in acting (Holley Reeves, 2016).

Apart from the four roles above, PR also has an implementation model for its duties and functions. In the view of James Grunig (1992), there are four models of PR communication practices, including their relationship to the implementation of CSR programs: Publicity or press agency, public information two-way asymmetrical, and two-way symmetrical.

RESEARCH METHOD

The study used the case study method (Yin, 1994); (Yin, 2004); (Yin, 2009), with a single case type (Yin, 2009). The phenomenon involving local mass media in CSR program communication is classified as a unique category (Stake, 1995) (Denzin, 1994). Data were collected through in-depth interviews with 25 informants from various elements, with the following criteria:

Table 1. Criteria for Research Informants

Element	Amount	Tiers	Information
EMCL Partner NGOs	4	Regency	Local NGOs
Local independent NGOs	2	Regency	Local NGOs
Regional independent NGOs	1	Province	Regional NGOs
Government	4	Regency/village	Regional development planning agency/Village head
ExxonMobil Cepu Limited	1	Multinational	Multinational company
EMCL CSR beneficiaries	11	Village	Benefit recipients
Mass media	2	Local	Print/online
Total	25	-	-

Source: Author (2025)

Research data analysis (Yin, 2009) consists of five phases: categorical grouping, direct interpretation, establishing patterns and finding correspondences, cross-case synthesis, and naturalistic generalization. The first is categorical grouping. Researchers try to find data categories related to CSR communication messages at this stage—the second, direct interpretation. Researchers look at single examples and draw out their meaning. Among other things, they interpret CSR communication messages constructed by local mass media. The third, establishing patterns and finding correspondence. Researchers try to find patterns and relationships from the informants' answers in this phase. The fourth, cross-case synthesis. In this phase, researchers looked for local mass media CSR communication characteristics—and, The fifth, naturalistic generalization. The researcher concluded the CSR communication message from the interpretation of data from the previous data analysis stages.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

ExxonMobil Cepu Limited CSR Program Partner

The EMCL CSR program developed in Indonesia consists of four pillars, namely: education, health, infrastructure, and economic development. In implementing CSR, the company collaborated with third parties as program partners. The partners ranged from NGOs to universities. The following is the data of partners for the EMCL CSR program for the last five years (2017-2022), as in table 2:

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Table 2: ExxonMobil Cepu Ltd CSR Program Partner in 2017–2022

Source: ExxonMobil Cepu Limited, processed (author, 2025)

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the company's commitment to involving local partners in Bojonegoro was quite high. Of the 33 EMCL program partners in 2017, 20 of them, or more than 60 percent were partners from Bojonegoro Regency, both NGOs and universities. There was a decrease in the number of local partners in 2018, but from 2019 to 2022 the number of local partners implementing EMCL's CSR programs was above 65 percent. The number of local partners reached 79 percent in 2022, while non-local partners were around 21 percent. The data above shows the company's commitment to cooperating with local partners was very strong.

ExxonMobil Cepu Limited CSR Program Fasilitator

Referring to the 2020 CSR companion partner data, EMCL included three partners that were not legal foundations (NGOs) or universities. However, youth organizations and women's organizations (OPP) were legal associations. The three organizations were the Anzor Youth Movement (GP), Muhammadiyah Youth, and Fatayat NU. GP Anzor is a youth organization affiliated with Nahdlatul Ulama (NU). Likewise, Fatayat NU is a young women's organization affiliated with NU. Apart from involving GP Anzor, EMCL also involved Muhammadiyah Youth as partners. Muhammadiyah Youth is an autonomous organization affiliated to Muhammadiyah.

Based on the researchers' notes, it was only in 2020 that EMCL involved OPP as a program partner. So far, EMCL has never involved OPP as a partner in running the PPM (Community Development Program) in the Bojonegoro, Tuban (East Java Province) or Blora (Central Java Province) areas. As far as the researchers' observations are concerned, the company has only involved GP Anzor, Pemuda Muhammadiyah, and Fatayat as activity partners. So far, EMCL has only supported the activities of the GP Anzor, Muhammadiyah Youth, and Fatayat NU organizations. However, with the inclusion of these three OPPs as program partners, EMCL's CSR program communicators have expanded, from previously only local and non-local NGOs, as well as universities, to youth organizations, that are affiliated with community organizations.

The involvement of these three OPPs was considered appropriate because all three are youth organizations that have networks down to the lowest base level, the village (branch). By involving those three, EMCL was assisted in conveying information about CSR programs to stakeholders in target villages. The existence of these three OPPs completed the fragment of elements that have accessed the EMCL CSR program in several years, with a role as a facilitator or implementer of CSR programs.

a. Collaboration in Informing CSR Programs

Apart from collaborating with NGOs and local universities as facilitators of CSR programs, EMCL also collaborates with local mass media to inform stakeholders about CSR programs. Based on the research results, there are four collaboration patterns between companies and local mass media. Namely, invitations for coverage, sending news releases to all mass media, cooperation contracts for advertising, and exploration of fostered partners.

The first pattern is an invitation to coverage. This pattern is carried out by the Company and program implementing partners (NGOs) by inviting local mass media to cover the opening or inauguration of the program. Also, news releases are sent by companies and NGOs implementing the program. The process of sending invitations for coverage to the mass media is carried out by companies in various ways. Invitations for coverage are made via WhatsApp or email. If a release is sent, the channel used is email. Because photos usually accompany it, so you ask when it will be broadcast. Writing the release was assisted with guidance from the Company. The second pattern is sending news releases to all mass media. Sending news releases does not coincide with activities. Companies need to make corrections, anticipate name spelling errors, etc. So, it requires approval from SKK Migas (Special Task Force for Upstream Oil and Gas Business Activities), the state agency that serves as the oil regulator. Besides company initiatives, news

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releases are sent out by NGOs or foundations implementing CSR programs. The Company highly recommends releases from partners.

The mass media has an editorial policy in response to news releases from CSR partner companies and NGOs. They were, the first, reporting ethics. Among the policies carried out by the media is editing according to the Press Council standards—the second, validation and confirmation. If the content of a news release is deemed to potentially not comply with the media company's policy, it will not be broadcast.

The third pattern is cooperation between local mass media and companies through advertising cooperation contracts. Generally, what is collaborated is in the form of editorial advertising or advertorials. Companies involve almost all forms of local mass media in communicating CSR to broad stakeholders.

"EMCL maximizes external communication channels to communicate CSR, including local mass media in various forms." (BW Interview, December 1, 2022)

Based on data mining in the field, data was obtained on several media partners with the Company in conveying CSR program information to the public, as in Table 3 below:

Table 3. Local Mass Media of ExxonMobil Cepu Limited CSR Partners

Name of Mass Media	Collaboration Material	Characteristic
Jawa Pos Radar Bojonegoro	Advertorials, news releases, covering events	Annual contract
Blok Bojonegoro.Com	Advertorials, news releases, covering events	Annual contract
Beritabojonegoro.com	Advertorials, news releases, covering events	Tentative
Suarabojonegoro.com	Advertorials, news releases, covering events	Tentative
Suarabanyuurip.com	Advertorials, news releases, covering events	Tentative
Jawa Timur TV (JTv)	Advertorials, covering events	Tentative
SBI FM, Istana FM	Advertorials, talk show	Tentative

Source: Author (2025)

Construction of CSR Communication Messages: Contribution, Concern, and Good Neighbors

The format for writing CSR program information, including patterns of invitations, coverage, and releases, has the same thing: it contains the company's goodness.' The difference is that the writing model uses the straight news technique if you write a short news release or reportage. The key sentences that appear in the news are (1) The company's contribution to the surrounding community, (2) Company concern, and (3) Being a good neighbor.

The format for conveying CSR program information content through advertorials emphasizes the human interest aspect, emphasizing the "goodness" of the company. The CSR program information content format is advertorials, mainly soft news with feature writing techniques and human interest exploration. The writing pattern starts from the problems that the beneficiaries face and is adjusted to the program pillars, namely education, health, and economy, which NGOs and corporate partners run. At the end of the article, there is a message of commitment from the company represented by the leadership of EMCL.

Several important, interesting, distinctive terms are found in the advertorial mechanism in local mass media. The first, public relations service. This term is used by local mass media, especially the editorial division, to serve clients who have "cooperated" in advertising or advertorials. Two company partners conduct public relations services, print media, and local online media. A form of public relations service is providing bonuses for reporting on the company's or its partners' social activities. Local print media and company partners carry out this model. Meanwhile, other online-based media partners use other public relations services, namely display advertising on the website homepage.

The second, use the asterisk (*). Local print media often use an asterisk (*) at the end of CSR advertorial articles. Generally, advertisements in the form of writing always have an advertorial written at the end of the article. According to an informant from the print media, KZA, using the asterisk (*) is a mass media company policy, in this case, a "compromise" between the advertising and editorial divisions.

The asterisk is a common sign that it is an advertorial. It is just that the advertorial text is not conspicuous but is replaced with an asterisk (*). Using star codes instead of advertorial words is sometimes at the client's request. Meanwhile, a different term is used by online media, namely information advertorial (infotorial), even though it is also included in the advertorial category.

"Our language is indeed infotorial, even though it is also advertorial, it is for differentiation. The consideration is service." (MAQ, Interview, November 28, 2022)

In advertorial writing, key sentences appear in the mass media. The crucial sentences constructed by the local mass media in reporting are (a) The company's contribution to the surrounding community, (b) Company concern, and (c) As a good neighbor. The CSR program message format emphasized by the company is shown in table 4:

Table 4. Content of CSR Program Messages in Local Mass Media

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News Type	Highlighted Message Content
Straight News	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In the form of releases and invitations for coverage. • Written by company or NGO, acc EMCL. • Writing media with a guide. • Characteristic of company and partner (NGO) activities in CSR programs. • The content of the message is <u>informative and ceremonial</u>.
Soft News	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Material containing advertorials, writers from EMCL communication media or media crew with the company's approval. • Human interest in writing characters and stories about the human side behind the program. • Highlight concern for residents.
Keywords	Important sentences in the news: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Company contribution to the surrounding community; 2. Company concern; And 3. Be a good neighbor.
Editorial Policy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The mass media uses the term relationship service to help EMCL. • Use an asterisk (*) and the author's initials at the end of the advertorial, as if it looks like news. • Replace the term advertorial with information advertorial (infotorial). • The font used is also the same as other news.

Source: Author (2025)

The fourth pattern is the promotion of company partners through documentary films—this model information dissemination with different concepts. The Company does not emphasize CSR programs but places more emphasis on promoting the Company's fostered partners, together with partner NGOs.

"It is not a film, but a documentary. "So we have the *Ayo Pinarak Bojonegoro* program; we offer it to companies, and they agree." (MAQ Interview, November 28, 2022)

The mechanism is to explore tourist locations in Bojonegoro Regency. This CSR communication model was created by online mass media. There is a host whose job is to guide the trip. Next, the host visited one tourist location after another in Bojonegoro. At the end of the scene, the host looks for souvenirs at a stand belonging to partner companies and NGOs.

The fifth pattern is placing display advertisements in mass media, as conveyed by informant KZA, Chief Editor of print mass media, Jawa Pos Radar Bojonegoro. The company's communications media team usually prepares display advertising designs. However, it is sometimes prepared by the editorial team of print mass media, who are partners. Display advertising is installed at two moments, namely, commemorating certain days, such as the Independence Day of the Republic of Indonesia. Placing display advertising is a form of Migtra mass media relations service for the support provided by EMCL. In other words, display advertising is a mass media initiative as a form of gratitude for EMCL's sponsorship of activities or events organized by print mass media. Or it is an advertising package from the mass media itself.

Self-Sufficiency through Local Mass Media Networks

The Company's collaboration with local mass media fosters the independence of radio mass media partners. Researchers found the use of radio media to disseminate CSR information independently. The Company uses the radio network to disseminate information/messages through talk shows and as a collaboration space with other oil and gas companies that also operate in Bojonegoro. This radio network does not collaborate directly with the Company in conveying CSR program information.

This network was initially part of a journalist capacity-building program organized by EMCL by establishing the Bojonegoro Radio Forum (FRB). FRB activists volunteered to facilitate public relations activities for oil and gas companies via radio during its development. The Company uses this network to disseminate program information via radio, especially talk shows.

The use of radio mass media to inform CSR independently in its development is not only for EMCL's CSR activities. However, it was also by other oil and gas companies operating in Bojonegoro Regency. Radio was chosen because the target was to disseminate this information to the villages in the Company's operational area. Among the oil and gas companies using this radio network are Pertamina EP Cepu, Jambaran Tiung Biru (JTB) gas field operator, Ngasem, Bojonegoro Regency.

b. Collaboration in Interaction with Local Mass Media

Researchers found three collaboration patterns implemented by companies in their interactions with local mass media. The first pattern is a regularly scheduled media gathering or gathering with journalists (print, electronic, and online media). During the Media Gathering, companies are not only represented by public relations or CSR PICs, but also the leader. They mingle with the mass media crew.

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The second pattern is thematic discussion. Discussions are held periodically while drinking coffee together. Many topics are discussed. Starting from company breakthroughs to new trends, for example, TikTok. The third pattern is increasing the capacity of journalists. As a form of reciprocal cooperation, the Company has held capacity-building activities several times that can support the capacity and ability of journalists in their work—for example, investigative journalism training.

Apart from that, companies often invite local mass media journalists to be involved in national and international oil and gas exhibition activities as an update on developments in the global oil and gas world. The Company also invites local mass media to conduct direct visits to oil and gas drilling locations and CSR programs.

Based on the data presented above, it can be concluded from the model that the collaboration between local mass media and the Company in ExxonMobil Cepu Limited's CSR communication consists of several steps, as depicted in Figure 1 below:

Figure 1. Local and Corporate Mass Media Collaboration Model in ExxonMobil Cepu Limited CSR Communication

Source: Author (2025)

c. Cultivating a Take-and-give Atmosphere

Referring to research data, it can be analyzed that EMCL combines press agency and two-way symmetric models in its collaboration with local mass media regarding CSR communication. Two-way symmetric is an ideal model from Grunig (2008). In this case, the public is depicted as respecting and providing something meaningful as an image of the organization that supports the company's work.

This model considers that the public is not just a passive recipient; the public can also act as a source so that message exchange or dialogue occurs. Organizations not only receive feedback from their public but can also respond positively by seeking unity. The two-way symmetric model can create a take-and-give atmosphere where organizations and the public strive to achieve consensus and collaboration (Kriyantono, 2017, p. 97).

This can be seen from the self-sufficiency of local mass media in disseminating CSR information, especially on radio networks, even though they are no longer tied to cooperation with companies. Referring to Grunig's (2008) view, the mass media public, in this case, has played a role not only as a passive recipient but also as a source who takes the initiative to convey CSR information to the public, resulting in an exchange of messages or dialogue.

EMCL's CSR communication collaboration pattern with local mass media consists of two forms: collaborate, involve, and inform. (a) Collaborate. Collaboration is carried out by EMCL by collaborating in contractual advertorials with mass media (print, online, and electronic). Advertorial content prepared by the EMCL team or media crew. (b) Involve and Inform. The mass media then informs the broader public of advertorials (also releases and coverage) of CSR programs. On their initiative (self-help), radio networks and partner mass media also communicate CSR programs to the public. The results of this research are also in line with references from the International Association for Public Participation (2018).

Thus, the minor proposition that can be drawn from this research is the collaborative pattern of CSR communication between oil companies and mass media clusters in Indonesia, especially in Bojonegoro Regency, East Java Province, which is carried out through collaboration, information, and involvement. The company carries out a communication function to publish CSR programs to the mass media cluster. The extent of relationships and business cooperation between mass media and oil and gas companies influences the collaborative pattern of company CSR communication to the mass media cluster. These minor propositions indicate that

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collaboration between mass media companies and oil and gas companies affects the mass media's self-sufficiency in communicating CSR programs to the public.

However, it must be admitted that this approach still has weaknesses. So far, CSR news has mostly been an informative program. Meanwhile, information regarding the Company's CSR issues or concerns has not been published over several years or strategically. For this reason, a CSR roadmap should be transparently presented to the public. The main problem that still stands out in this aspect is transparency.

CSR communication is essential in leaving a suitable corporate footprint (Ham & Kim, 2019b), one of which is by conveying information honestly to the public. Because transparency is the moral basis for business behavior, transparency can help organizations appear trustworthy through CSR communication through various channels, such as research (Henriques, 2007) (Ihlen et al., 2011).

This finding contradicts with the view (Holme & Watts, 2000) in Rusdianto (2013). The more transparent the company is in the aspects demanded by all its stakeholders, its reputation will be higher. This is in contrast to the findings above. This means the company's reputation will decrease if there is less transparency.

On the other hand, using asterisks (*), public relations services, and key sentences in advertorials are new research findings. The use of keywords as a form of corporate concern, the company's contribution to the surrounding community, and as a good neighbor, referring to Morsing (2006) (Jonker, 2006), is a core message concept that does not automatically appear, but is the result of internal and external analysis that carefully.

These three essential sentences are the company's efforts to demonstrate objective claims (results), as Mette Morsing (2006) required in conveying the content of CSR program messages. The use of these three key sentences is a construction built by the company to create EMCL credibility, as well as an effort to achieve stakeholder legitimacy, which examines the relationship between CSR communication credibility and company legitimacy through website content analysis (Lock & Schulz-Knappe, 2019). The findings of this research are new; researchers have never found them in previous research.

CONCLUSION

The research explores the collaboration model between local mass media and oil and gas companies, especially EMCL, in communicating CSR to stakeholders. Based on the data presentation and discussion, it can be concluded that collaboration between local mass media and companies leads to press agency and two-way symmetry, which is developed through an approach to informing and interacting patterns.

Collaboration on information patterns found that the messages conveyed by local mass media in the construction of CSR messages focused on three key sentences: the company's contribution, the company's form of concern, and the form of a good neighbor. Meanwhile, in interaction patterns, the company supports various journalist activities, especially those related to increasing the capacity of local mass media journalists.

These two collaboration patterns foster a take-and-give relationship through self-sufficiency from local mass media networks, especially radio networks, which voluntarily help communicate the company's CSR program to the broader public. In this case, the local mass media respects and provides something meaningful as a picture of stakeholders who support the company's work. Local mass media is not only a passive recipient but can also act as a source so that message exchange or dialogue occurs. The relationship between local mass media and the company can create a take-and-give atmosphere where the company and the public try to reach a consensus and collaborate.

However, this research has limitations. This research only captures collaboration between companies and local mass media in communicating CSR programs to the public. For this reason, researchers recommend that future research be able to capture collaboration in CSR communication carried out by companies with the government and CSR partner NGOs—or photographing collaboration in CSR communication between companies and national scale mass media.

REFERENCES

- 1) Anderson, C. L., & Bieniaszewska, R. L. (2005). Expansion into New Territories. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 9(1), 1–9.
- 2) Buldybayeva, G. (2014). Both sides of CSR practice: A case from oil and gas industry in Kazakhstan. *Acta Polytechnica Hungarica*.
- 3) Denzin, N. K. (1994). Introduction: Entering the field of qualitative research. *Handbook of Qualitative Research*.
- 4) Dobebe, A. R., Westberg, K., Steel, M., & Flowers, K. (2014). An Examination of Corporate Social Responsibility Implementation and Stakeholder Engagement: A Case Study in the Australian Mining Industry. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 23(3), 145–159. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.1775>
- 5) Ellerup Nielsen, A., & Thomsen, C. (2018). Reviewing corporate social responsibility communication: a legitimacy perspective. *Corporate Communications*, 23(4), 492–511. <https://doi.org/10.1108/CCIJ-04-2018-0042>

- 6) Grunig, James E. (1992). *Excellent in Public Relations & Communication Management*. New Jersey: Lawrence Associate, pp. 65–90
- 7) Grunig, J. E., & Grunig, L. A. (2008). Excellence theory in public relations: Past, present, and future. In *Public relations research: European and international perspectives and innovations* (pp. 327-347). Wiesbaden: VS Verlag für Sozialwissenschaften.
- 8) Gulbrandsen, L. H., & Moe, A. (2014). Oil Company CSR Collaboration in New Petro-States. *Journal of Corporate Citizenship*, 2005(20), 53–64. <https://doi.org/10.9774/gleaf.4700.2005.wi.00008>
- 9) Ham, C. D., & Kim, J. (2019a). The effects of CSR communication in corporate crises: Examining the role of dispositional and situational CSR skepticism in context. *Public Relations Review*, May, 101792. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pubrev.2019.05.013>
- 10) Ham, C. D., & Kim, J. (2019b). The Role of CSR in Crises: Integration of Situational Crisis Communication Theory and the Persuasion Knowledge Model. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 158(2), 353–372. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-017-3706-0>
- 11) Henriques, A. (2007). *Corporate truth: The limits to transparency*. London: Earthscan.
- 12) Holley, Reeves (2016). “Defining Public Relations’ Role in Corporate Social Responsibility Programs”. PR Journal Vol. 10, No. 2 (Summer/Fall 2016), page 1-19
- 13) Holme, R., & Watts, P. (2000). Corporate social responsibility: Making good business sense. WBCSD
- 14) Ihlen, Ø., Bartlett, J. L., & May, S. (2011). The Handbook of Communication and Corporate Social Responsibility. In *The Handbook of Communication and Corporate Social Responsibility*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118083246>
- 15) International Association for Public Participation. (2018). IAP2’S Public Participation Spectrum. Retrieved December 12, 2022, from www.iap2.org.au
- 16) Jaworska, S. (2018). Change But no Climate Change: Discourses of Climate Change in Corporate Social Responsibility Reporting in the Oil Industry. *International Journal of Business Communication*, 55(2), 194–219. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2329488417753951>
- 17) Jonker, J. (2006). *Management models for corporate social responsibility*. Springer.
- 18) Joseph, I., & Elda, N. (2019). www.econstor.eu.
- 19) Kriyantono, Rakhmat. (2017). *Teori-Teori Public Relations Perspektif Barat dan Lokal*. Cetakan II. Jakarta: Kencana, Prenada Media Group
- 20) Kross, K. (2013). Corporate social responsibility (CSR). In *Profession and Purpose: A Resource Guide for MBA Careers in Sustainability*. https://doi.org/10.9774/gleaf.978-1-907643-08-8_12
- 21) Littlejohn, Foss, Oetzel (2017). *Theories of Human Communication, Eleven Edition*, Waveland Press, Inc., Illinois, USA
- 22) Liu, A. A., & Lewis, G. (2019). *From HSE to Sustainability : CSR Disclosure by Oil Companies*. 13–15.
- 23) Lock, I., & Schulz-Knappe, C. (2019). Credible corporate social responsibility (CSR) communication predicts legitimacy: Evidence from an experimental study. *Corporate Communications*, 24(1), 2–20. <https://doi.org/10.1108/CCIJ-07-2018-0071>
- 24) Ma, L., & Bentley, J. M. (2022). Can strategic message framing mitigate the negative effects of skeptical comments against corporate-social-responsibility communication on social networking sites? ☆. *Public Relations Review*, 48(4), 102222. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pubrev.2022.102222>
- 25) Moreno, A., & Capriotti, P. (2009). Communicating CSR, citizenship and sustainability on the web. *Journal of Communication Management*, 13(2), 157–175. <https://doi.org/10.1108/13632540910951768>
- 26) Morsing, M. (2006). Corporate social responsibility as strategic auto-communication: on the role of external stakeholders for member identification. *Business Ethics: A European Review*, 15(2), 171–182. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8608.2006.00440.x>
- 27) Pujihartati, S. H., Nurhaeni, I. D. A., Kartono, D. T., & Demartoto, A. (2023). New Media and Green Behaviour Campaign Through Corporate Social Responsibility Collaboration. *Jurnal Komunikasi: Malaysian Journal of Communication*, 39(2), 325–337. <https://doi.org/10.17576/JKMJC-2023-3902-18>
- 28) Rahmanto, Andre. (2010), *Wacana Corporate Social Responsibility dalam Website Perusahaan*, ISSN: 1411-268, Jurnal Komunikasi Massa, Vol. 3
- 29) Rizal, A. R. A., Abang Ahmad, D. A. M., & Raslie, H. (2022). Conceptualising the Role of Opinion Leaders as Moderator to Local Communities Commitment in Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) Communication. *Jurnal Komunikasi: Malaysian Journal of Communication*, 38(4), 425–441. <https://doi.org/10.17576/JKMJC-2022-3804-24>
- 30) Rudy, May. 2005. *Komunikasi & Hubungan Masyarakat Internasional*. Bandung: Refika Aditama
- 31) Rusdianto, Ujang. (2013). *CSR Communications: A Framework for PR Practitioners (Cet. 1)*. Yogyakarta. Graha Ilmu

- 32) Siegel, D., & McWilliams, A. (2006). *Corporate Social Responsibility : A Theory of the Firm Perspective Author (s) : Academy of Management is collaborat ...*
- 33) Stake, R. E. (1995). *The Art of Case Study Research*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- 34) Tanaya, Jimmy. (2004). *Tanggung Jawab Sosial Korporasi: Sebuah Pengantar*. The Business Watch Indonesia-Widya Sari Press. Surakarta
- 35) Tanaya, J. (2013). *Corporate Social Responsibility: A Framework for Analysing Csr Heterogeneity Through the Case of Indonesian Palm Oil. PQDT - UK & Ireland*, 280.
- 36) Tench, R., Sun, W., & Jones, B. (2014). Introduction: CSR communication as an emerging field of study. In *Critical Studies on Corporate Responsibility, Governance and Sustainability* (Vol. 6). Emerald Group Publishing Limited. [https://doi.org/10.1108/S2043-9059\(2014\)0000006025](https://doi.org/10.1108/S2043-9059(2014)0000006025)
- 37) Tewari, R., & Dave, D. (2012). Corporate Social Responsibility: Communication through Sustainability Reports by Indian and Multinational Companies. *Global Business Review*, 13(3), 393–405. <https://doi.org/10.1177/097215091201300303>
- 38) Widhagdha, M. F., Wahyuni, H. I., & Sulhan, M. (2019). Bonding, bridging and linking relationships of the csr target communities of PT pertamina refinery unit II sungai pakning. *Jurnal Komunikasi: Malaysian Journal of Communication*, 35(4), 470–483. <https://doi.org/10.17576/JKMJC-2019-3504-29>
- 39) Wilcox, T. (2006). Human resource development as an element of corporate social responsibility. *Asia Pacific Journal of Human Resources*, 44(2), 184–196. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1038411106066395>
- 40) Yang, A., & Liu, W. (2020). CSR Communication and Environmental Issue Networks in Virtual Space: A Cross-National Study. *Business and Society*, 59(6), 1079–1109. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0007650318763565>
- 41) Yin, R. K. (1994). Discovering the future of the case study. Method in evaluation research. *Evaluation Practice*, 15(3), 283–290.
- 42) Yin, R. K. (2004). *The case study anthology*. Sage.
- 43) Yin, R. K. (2009). *Case study research: Design and methods* (Vol. 5). sage.